

The Intersection of Online and In-Person Identities of Teachers: Insights from Their Students

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Abstract

The rapid shift to online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted the way teachers interact with their students. This study explored how students perceive their teachers' online and in-person identities in a higher education institution in Davao City, Philippines. A phenomenological research design was employed to gather data through in-depth interviews with six students who have experienced both online and in-person learning modalities. The findings revealed significant differences in student perceptions of teacher identity across these two modes of delivery. Students perceived their teachers as more approachable and engaging in in-person classes, while online interactions were often characterized as less personal and formal. Additionally, students noted differences in teaching styles, lesson delivery, and overall teacher presence between the two modes. These findings highlight the importance of understanding the complex interplay between teacher identity, technology, and student learning experiences. By examining the impact of online learning on teacher-student relationships, this study contributes to a deeper understanding of the evolving role of teachers in the digital age.

Keywords: *Online Identities, In-Person Identities, Teachers, Students, Insights.*

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Introduction

This global pandemic has led to the loss of learning, which has had a significant impact on many teachers, families, and children across the country. Scholars in the education sector estimate that children in the United States could have lost up to a full year's worth of learning from a three-month closure (Dorn et al., 2020). The loss of learning is a situation that translates to the loss of skills among teachers who were used to in-person instruction despite delivering online, which could be the most feasible approach left (Aguiera & Nightengale-Lee, 2020). Capahay

(2020) stated that "Online education is an inevitable option to decongest classrooms amid physical or social distancing protocol might help mitigate COVID-19 transmission in schools". Another situation that is causing distress for educators, is that some may not be getting paid or must take their sick leave or vacation time if they do not return to in-person instruction (North, 2020). Teachers across New York State have been using different resources to support learning during the COVID-19 pandemic (NYSED, 2020). Some teachers have utilized online platforms where teachers interact with their students in various learning sessions (Code et al., 2020).

At the University of the Philippines – Open University (UPOU), a single-mode DE institution in the Philippines, the term "open and distance e-learning" (ODEL) has been coined to refer to the new mode of online or Web-based DE. More specifically, ODeL refers to "forms of education provision that use contemporary technologies to enable varied combinations of synchronous and asynchronous

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communication among learners and educators who are physically separated from one another for part or all of the educational experience" (Alfonso, 2012, n.p.). ODeL expands the term "open and distance learning" or ODL to include use of e-learning or online learning methodologies to enable multiple forms of interaction and dialogue that can bridge the distance between teachers and learners (Anderson, 2008c; Calvert, 2005; Garrison, 2009) and provide access to a vast array of interactive and multimedia learning resources that can be used to design learning environments for learners in diverse circumstances (Bates, 2008; Haughey, Evans & Murphy, 2008; Tait, 2010). Using online portals and VLEs further enables DE institutions to support both independent learning and collaborative learning through "increasingly complex pedagogical structures" (Haughey et al., 2008, p. 15).

The advent of the digital age has significantly transformed the way individuals present themselves to the world, and the teaching profession is no exception. As education has increasingly migrated to online platforms, the nature of teacher identity has undergone a fundamental shift, particularly in the Davao region (Elmido, 2022). One of the key challenges facing teachers in the Davao region is the need to navigate the complexities of their online presence. While the use of technology in education can enhance the learning experience, it also requires teachers to develop new skills and competencies to effectively engage with their students in a virtual setting. The COVID-19 pandemic has further exacerbated this issue, forcing educators to quickly adapt their teaching practices to accommodate remote learning. Students in Davao City face challenges in using learning management systems and online payment platforms, highlighting the need for mutual understanding and information dissemination to adapt to technology-based learning.

According to a study on the digital competencies of teachers in higher education, many educators felt overwhelmed and unprepared to use online or remote teaching strategies, and they struggled to adapt their pedagogy to the new challenges posed by the pandemic, such as unreliable internet access and shifting educational directives (Gómez-Pablos et al., 2022). Similar findings were reported in a study on teachers' online teaching experiences in the Netherlands, where researchers noted that several teachers experienced difficulties when using distance learning technologies due to a lack of familiarity (Huang et al., 2021).

Understanding the interplay of teachers' online and in-person identities, especially from the perspective of student's experiences and perceptions, better is a critical research gap that this study aims to address. Due in large part to the COVID-19 pandemic's quick shift to online learning settings, teacher-student relationships have changed dramatically. This underscores the necessity of examining how students view instructors' identities in a variety of learning situations and the changing nature of the teacher-student relationship. Policies and programs that can support and protect teachers and students during this time of rapid change in the education sector need to be informed by further research on this topic, given the significant impact of the pandemic on learning loss and the difficulties teachers and students face in adjusting to technology-based education.

Considering the context of this study, it aims to provide significant insights into teachers' in-person and online identities that would ultimately help craft policies and programs that aim to protect both teachers and students through the Department of Education, Commission on Higher Education, and Local Government Units. Furthermore, it will also aim to give teachers and students an avenue to share their experiences and knowledge about in-person and online identities especially since most teachers and students are engaged in the online world due to the changes in our education system. Additionally, it will help future researchers to engage in further research about this phenomenon to provide a more nuanced understanding of the differences in social identities in our society.

The study was anchored to the Social Identity Theory of Tajfel and Turner in 1979. This theory states that individuals tend to have different identities due to different group memberships (McLeod, 2023). The theory fits on this study since it will help us understand why individuals, particularly teachers, present different identities depending on who are they interacting with. This also explains the idea of conformity towards different norms in online or in-person identities.

Literature Review

Identity is seen as a fundamental component of teachers' professional development (Beijaard 2019). Teacher identity is a complex network of influences and imprints shaped by personal and professional life experiences (Bukor, 2014). Teachers therefore face the policies and professional discourses they meet not as *tabula rasae*, but rather actively employ their prior identities to understand, learn from, assess, and adapt to the changing circumstances of their work in schools and classrooms (Buchanan, 2015).

Good engagement between instructors and students will establish great relationships in the classroom and contribute to successful learning (Che Amad et al., 2017). Teacher-student interaction is essential in all types of education, regardless of whether technology is engaged (Kuo et al., 2014). Students' interactions with educators are crucial as a strong, favorable interaction between the student and the teacher is essential for enhancing students' behavioral engagement (Nguyen et al., 2018).

According to Keiler (2018), drastic changes in the learning environment might have an impact on instructors' identities and teaching styles. It is believed that teacher identity has a significant impact on teachers' choices about instructional techniques, the substance of instruction, teacher-student interactions, and professional development (Hahl et al., 2018). However, recent technological breakthroughs, notably in digitally mediated teaching and learning, as well as extensive use of social media in education, have had a transforming influence on language and identity (Darvin 2016).

Students typically swayed away from taking online courses due to previous negative experiences such as an unprecedented workload, lack of interaction with professors, lack of professor presence, malfunctioning electronic devices difficulties with self-teaching, and time management (Banks & Vergez, 2022). Most students missed personal interaction with the instructor and their peers and indicated that they found in-person interactions more effective than online discussions (Ghazi-Saidi et al., 2020). Moreso, Many students believe that online interactions are less personal and more formal, which might cause anxiety while interacting or asking questions. Students noted that actions like contributing responses or being called upon were more daunting in online settings, most likely owing to the dread of being assessed in a less familiar setting (Jaggars, 2014).

As stated by Ulla et al. Al (2024) teacher identity has gained widespread recognition as an essential element of the teaching profession that has a significant influence on teachers' attitudes, actions, and comprehension of their social duties. According to Reeves (2018), the process of forming an identity as a teacher requires a great deal of work to create and reassess their teaching identities. Students may observe the teacher's appearance, age, facial expression, physical manner, hairdo, and clothes in a classroom context. Students may nonetheless see these characteristics as indicators of experience, time, or metacognitive awareness even when they have little to do with subject content or instructional ability (Dennen and Arslan, 2022).

Materials and Methods

The researchers employ a qualitative phenomenological research design to present the lived experiences of the participants of the study. Quantitative research utilizes the exploration and understanding of the social or human problem through emerging questions and procedures that help reveal general themes of the participant's responses (Creswell & Creswell, 2022). Additionally, phenomenological research focuses on presenting the lived experiences of the participants on a particular phenomenon. This involves a small number of participants through extensive and prolonged engagements (Creswell & Creswell, 2022).

The researchers selected 6 students in Davao City through a purposive sampling technique and adhered to the study's inclusion and exclusion criteria. To be admitted as one of the participants of this study, the participants were required to possess the following: Male, Female or members of LGBTQIA+, 18-30 years old, a student currently enrolled for 2 consecutive semesters in any higher education institution and must have experienced online and in-person teaching with the same teacher in the same semester. In short, the student is/was engaged in hybrid/flexible learning in the same semester. The respondents were

not admitted to the study on the following grounds: the respondent's age was not included in the age bracket provided above and were not enrolled during the present school year.

The researchers will craft an unstructured interview guide questionnaire based on the objective of the study. To ensure the reliability and validity of the questionnaire, the interview guide is examined by qualified individuals in the field. This questionnaire includes open-ended questions that would help the researchers collect data coming from the experiences of the participants. The data gathering through the use of interviews will be done through face-to-face method. To determine who will be admitted to the study, the researchers will administer informed consent forms to ensure that the participants will be informed about the background of the study, its associated risks and benefits. The data gathered from the study will be analyzed and interpreted through thematic analysis using the Colaizzi method.

The researchers will abide by the guidelines established by the Research Ethics Committee of their affiliated institution. These guidelines encompass various assessment criteria, including but not limited to social value, informed consent, risk, benefits, and safety, privacy and confidentiality, justice, transparency, qualification of researchers, adequacy of facilities, and community involvement. Furthermore, these protocols are by the standards outlined by the Department of Science and Technology – Philippine Health Research and Ethics Board (DOST-PHREB) under the Republic Act No. 10532, also known as the Philippine National Health Research System (PNHRS) Act of 2013. The researchers are committed to ensuring that all participants in the study are treated with the utmost respect and provided with the necessary protection, recognizing these elements as pivotal to the study's success.

Before initiating data collection for this study, the researchers will adhere to a structured sequence of steps. Firstly, they will submit a concept paper outlining the study's objectives to the professor responsible for overseeing the course on Qualitative Research Techniques and Utilization, seeking approval. Upon obtaining approval, the researchers will proceed to submit the unstructured interview guide questionnaire for validation with the experts in the field. Subsequently, the researchers will identify students who might be potential participants in the study considering the set inclusion and exclusion criteria of the study. Lastly, the researchers will engage the identified participants considering that they have read and understood the informed consent form and consented through signature that they are willing to participate in the study.

Results and Discussions

In this section, the result of the data analysis is presented. To give a comprehensive explanation of the themes, discussions are also provided. To refer to the students' quoted answers to the interview. The transcription of the interview found in the appendices.

Table 1. Students' Insights on their Teachers' In-Person and Online Identities

Main Themes	Sub-Themes
Interaction with the Teacher to their Students	Less interaction in Online Class, More interaction in In-Person classes
	Problems in shifting modes from in-person to online (i.e. intermittent internet connection).
	Less gestures can be seen in online than in in-person class.
Teachers' Teaching Style	Teacher-centered – online class; Student-centered – in-person class
	Students are hesitant to answer questions in online class than in-person class.
	Limited participation of students due to teachers' limited time
Teachers' Lesson Delivery	Students are scared to their teachers in online class than in in-person class.

	The students can understand the lesson better in in-person than in online class.
	The teachers are strict in their lessons in online than in in-person class.
Teachers' Overall Identity as an Educator as perceived by the students	Misconception on the identity of teachers' in online compared to in-person class.
	The students perceived the teachers as boring.
	Teachers are more friendly and approachable in in-person class.

Interaction with the Teacher to Their Students

Identity is seen as a fundamental component of teachers' professional development (Beijaard 2019). Teacher identity is a complex network of influences and imprints shaped by personal and professional life experiences (Bukor, 2014). It suggests that teachers' identities, formed by personal and professional experiences, play a crucial role in their interactions with students and overall teaching effectiveness. Based on our data analysis, the most prevalent students' insights are Less interaction in Online Class, more interaction in In-Person classes, Problems in shifting modes from in-person to online (i.e. intermittent internet connection), and Less gestures can be seen in online than in in-person class as shown in the table.

Less Interaction in Online Class, More Interaction in In-Person Classes. Online classes often present fewer opportunities for direct interaction between students and teachers. This can be attributed to the technological limitations and asynchronous nature of online learning. In contrast, in-person classes typically provide more opportunities for face-to-face interactions, fostering a stronger sense of community and facilitating deeper engagement with the material.

"... Maka paminaw ka ug tarong because maka eye contact man gud mo sa teacher. like naa moy interaction duha. May difference kasi pag sa online kay murag daghan ug mga confusion about ana and dili nimo dali dali ma contact si sir kay busy pd siya and as ano naman face to face dali lang nimo ma clarify kung unsa iyang mga instructions." (You can listen more attentively because you can make eye contact with the teacher. It's like you have a two-way interaction. Online classes are different because there's often a lot of confusion, and you can't easily reach your teacher because they're also busy. With face-to-face classes, you can quickly clarify their instructions.) --- P4, Lines 8-12

"...kay pag mag online class man gud kay more on stick ang teacher sa notes nako unsa iyang gina-ano Tapos, mas more on formal sila pag sa online, tapos in contrast sa face-to-face kay mas more on engaging sila tapos mas more on naay direct interaction ang student ug ang teacher." (...because during online classes, the teacher sticks more to the notes that I have, whatever he's doing. Then, they are more formal in online classes, and in contrast to face-to-face classes, they are more engaging and there is more direct interaction between the student and the teacher.) --- P1, Lines 34-37

The participant's responses highlight the perceived benefits of in-person classes in terms of interaction and engagement. Non-verbal cues, immediate feedback, and a sense of community are often cited as advantages of traditional classrooms. However, online classes can face challenges in these areas due to the lack of physical presence. To address this, educators can utilize interactive tools, encourage active participation, create a supportive community, and provide regular opportunities for feedback. By implementing these strategies, online classes can be made more engaging and interactive, fostering a positive learning experience for students. These corroborates to the study of Ghazi-Saidi et al. (2020) which stated that most students missed personal interaction with the instructor and their peers and indicated that they found in-person interactions more effective than online discussions.

Problems in shifting modes from in-person to online (i.e. intermittent internet connection). One significant problem in shifting from in-person to online learning is the frequent occurrence of intermittent internet connections, which can disrupt the flow of instruction and hinder effective communication between teachers and students.

“...Ginatawag niya pero dili mutubag. Example, I'm sorry sir, di ko ka answer kay binay akong net.” (Even when the teacher calls on me, I can't always respond. I often have to say, 'I'm sorry sir, my internet connection is slow.) --- P2, Lines 81-82

“... dili ko maka ask kung unsa ang pasabot kay manlaw mag ask kay murag because kay pasabot ana kay wala ka naminaw. On mn pd iyang camera but naay during mga internet connections na binay kayo nga dili nimo makita jud ang mga faces ng teachers.” (I can't ask for clarification because I'm embarrassed. It's like admitting that I wasn't listening. Even though their camera is on, there are times when the internet connection is so slow that I can't see the teachers' faces clearly.) --- P4, Lines 27-30

“...Akoa po, sir, is kanang in terms of online, kay kanang lisod kaayo ninyo ma-practice ang inyong gi-practice sa inyong discussion while sa face-to-face naman po is for example, madali lang ninyo siya ma-catch up or inyong ma-absorb for example, in online maghatag siya ng activity so activity lang, na tanan but in face-to-face pwede ka i-kanmustabon sa inyong teacher kung either na-gets ba ni mo or na ano ba.” (Sir, in my opinion, when it comes to online classes, it's difficult to practice what we've discussed compared to face-to-face classes. For example, in a face-to-face setting, it's easy to catch up or absorb the lesson. But in online classes, the teacher might just give an activity, and that's it. Whereas in a face-to-face setting, you can easily ask your teacher if you understand the lesson or not.) --- P2, Lines 58-62

Students typically swayed away from taking online courses due to previous negative experiences such as an unprecedented workload, lack of interaction with professors, lack of professor presence, malfunctioning electronic devices difficulties with self-teaching, and time management (Banks & Vergez, 2022). The participant's experience highlights the challenges faced by many students during the transition to online learning. The intermittent internet connection hindered their ability to see the teacher clearly, leading to confusion and a reluctance to ask for clarification due to fear of embarrassment. These challenges can negatively impact student engagement and academic performance.

Less gestures can be seen in online than in in-person class. The absence of gestures in online learning environments can significantly impact student comprehension and engagement. Limited visual fields, technical constraints, and cultural differences can hinder the visibility and effectiveness of gestures. To address this, educators can encourage active participation, utilize visual aids, promote a culture of engagement, and experiment with different camera angles. By incorporating more gestures and visual cues, online learning can become a more engaging and effective experience for students.

“...You can, you can see their gestures, their facial expressions, and while in in an online setting, you cannot because of the connection uhm. Sometimes they turn off their camera and sometimes they logged out from the meeting because of a slow connection. --- P4, Lines 7-10

“...Uhm... Si sir is pag face to face is mas ma ano namo siya, mas makita naman iyabang expressions, then iyabang interaction between us. Like, jolly siya magtudo sa moa si sir... then, mas malingaw kay like naa siyay yung ano yung ano, yung like gestures. (Uh, well, Sir is more engaging when we're face-to-face. We can see his expressions better and his interactions with us. Like, he's really fun when he teaches us in our module... and then, it's more enjoyable because, like, he has those, those, those, like gestures.) ---P3, Lines 30-33

The research participants emphasized the challenges of observing gestures and facial expressions in online classes due to technical constraints. They noted that these limitations can lead to decreased engagement and a less enjoyable learning experience compared to in-person classes. Students may observe the teacher's appearance, age, facial expression, physical manner, hairdo, and clothes in a classroom context. Students may nonetheless see these characteristics as indicators of experience, time, or metacognitive awareness even when they have little to do with subject content or instructional ability (Dennen and Arslan, 2022).

Teachers' Teaching Style

A teacher's teaching style is a crucial factor that can significantly impact student learning outcomes. Effective teaching styles often involve learner-centered approaches, differentiated instruction, positive

classroom management, subject matter expertise, and flexibility. By employing these strategies, teachers can create a positive and supportive learning environment that fosters student motivation, engagement, understanding, and positive attitudes towards learning. This corroborates to the study of Keiler (2018), drastic changes in the learning environment might have an impact on instructors' identities and teaching styles. It is believed that teacher identity has a significant impact on teachers' choices about instructional techniques, the substance of instruction, teacher-student interactions, and professional development (Hahl et al, 2008).

Teacher-centered – online class; Student-centered – in-person class. Teaching styles can significantly influence the learning experience, regardless of whether the class is online or in-person. Traditional styles like lecture-based and demonstration are often associated with online classes, while student-centered approaches like inquiry-based and cooperative learning are more common in in-person settings. However, both formats can accommodate various styles. The most effective teaching style depends on the subject matter, learning objectives, and student needs.

“...feel nako sir is kay pag teacher is not like pareha sa online na boring kaayo siya murag di makapaminaw ang mga students as iyaba then like pag boring kaayo ang lessons dili na lang mi maminaw sa iyaba. Um, like ano, sir, ah, ang mapansin nako sa mga teachers is, pagdili, ma, ano, ila, ay, pagdili ng maingon ang kanang, ano, is, mag, pasagdaan ng mga ila, sir, then ang iyabang attitude is, pasagdan, murag, ubmm... unsay tawag ana? Wait, sorry. Nakalimut ko sa term. Passive ang learning or? Passive ang learning, sir. Yes. Passive ang learning. The iyabang attitude towards sa amua is pasagdan na lang niya sa amua. Kami na lang magbahala sa amung learning.” (I feel, sir, that teaching is not the same as online. Online classes are very boring. It's like the students can't really listen to the teacher. And the lessons are so boring that we just stop listening. Um, like, sir, what I notice about teachers is that they tend to, well, what's the word? They let their students... they have a passive attitude towards their students. It's like they're saying, 'Okay, just do whatever you want.' Their attitude towards us is like, 'I'll just leave you to it.' We're the ones who have to take care of our own learning. I think it's called passive learning, sir. Yes, passive learning. Their attitude towards us is like, 'Just leave it up to you.) ---P3, Lines 51-59

“...Naga-ask sila pero as a student, pag naga-ask ko, ayun ako. Gets na lang ako para mahuman dayon ang klase. So mao gyud na siya sir. But in face to face kay maano mag-ano man gud sila? Like, kanang naa pud kay "hala, kailangan gyud nako niya siya tun-an kay pagkabuman ing-ani na pud ang bubaton.” (They ask questions, but as a student, when I ask, it feels like they just want me to understand so we can finish the class quickly. That's how it is, sir. But in a face-to-face setting, you're more motivated because you think, 'Oh, I really need to understand this because we're going to do something like this again.) P2, Lines 65-68

“...So kung sa online siya, based ako ang experience kay mas, ano siya, mas diretso-diretso lang gyud iyang ano pag mag klase, pag online diretso-diretso lang usahay mangutana siyag questions pero at the same time kay dili pud niya mapangutana usahay kay kulang pud sa oras ing-ana ug tungod pud sa signal so ma diretso-diretso lang gyud iyang klase unlike sa pag face to face kaya naa siyay at some point usahay gyud na kanang before mag klase mag mangutana siya sa amua kung naa ba mi overview about ana na topic ing-ana tapos pag during pud siya yung class, pag face-to-face, kay naa siyay kailangan manawag siyag mga students, ing-ana, i-ask, para kanang naa bay nahibal-an.”

According to Reeves (2018), the process of forming an identity as a teacher requires a great deal of work to create and reassess their teaching identities. In a teacher-centered approach, where the teacher serves as the primary authority and content expert, identity formation tends to focus on maintaining control and delivering knowledge. However, teachers must still reassess their methods to adapt to evolving educational demands. In contrast, a student-centered approach requires teachers to adopt a more flexible, facilitative role, continuously reshaping their identity to meet students' diverse learning needs. The participant's perception of online classes as boring and passive, along with their observation of a teacher-centered approach, supports this theme. However, individual experiences can vary, and both online and in-person classes can be either teacher-centered or student-centered, depending on various factors.

Students are hesitant to answer questions in online class than in-person class. Students are often more hesitant to answer questions in online classes compared to in-person classes. This is due to factors such as anonymity, technical difficulties, reduced nonverbal cues, cultural differences, and a lack of community.

“...I think as perspective sa teacher, wala siya na affect but as perception sa student maka affect siya kay ang student hesitant sa iyaba kay strict siya sa online and buotan diay siya sa personal or as face-to-face na setting.” (I think from the teacher's perspective, it didn't affect him much. But from the student's perspective, it can affect them because the students are hesitant towards him since he's strict online but is actually kind in person or in a face-to-face setting.) P4, Lines 64-67

“...Naa siyay mga questions sad sa amoa, then matubag mn pd namo siya pag face to face pero pag sa online kay hesitant kay dili namo makuba iyang point kay wala mn ko kapaminaw ug tarong pero naa pd instances na maka paminaw ko pag makapaminaw kaayo ko sa lesson pero pag di ko makapaminaw sa lesson... kung ma boringan ko sa lesson kay dra na nga time ma confuse ko kung unsa mn gyud gipasabot ni sir.” (He also has questions for us, and we can answer him when we meet face-to-face. But online, we're hesitant because we can't really get his point since I can't hear him properly. However, there are times when I can hear the lesson very well, but when I can't hear the lesson... or if I get bored with the lesson because it's already late, I get confused about what he is really trying to say.) --- P3, Lines 22-27

“...Iyaba lang pong the way siya mag-teach kaya for example, na siya sa online, kay more on discussion lang siya. Like, kanang manawag siya pero murag wala may mo response. But in face-to-face, kaya um, like, magtawag siya. So, mga estudyante is maka-cooperate yung siyag taman kay pwede na niya na patindugon ba ron or kanang tagaan niya ug other tasks po.” (It depends on how the teacher teaches. In online classes, they mostly have discussions but it's hard to get students to participate. But in real classrooms, teachers can call on students and the students can easily answer or do other tasks.) P2, Lines 73-77

“...Pero kung sa ako ang mga desisyon kay mas okayan ko sa face-to-face na classes kay naay mga direct interaction sa mga teacher na pwede ko maka-ask directly sa teacher kay naa may some point na pag online class kay binay ang signal unya di mangutana kay maulaw sa teacher ing ana.” (I prefer face-to-face classes because I can directly ask the teacher questions. In online classes, I often have a slow internet connection, and I feel shy about asking questions when that happens.) ---P1, Lines 41-45

According to Jaggars (2014) students noted that actions like contributing responses or being called upon were more daunting in online settings, most likely owing to the dread of being assessed in a less familiar setting. Students' hesitation to answer questions in online classes often stems from a combination of factors. The perceived strictness of the teacher online, coupled with technical difficulties like poor audio quality and internet connection issues, can create a daunting environment. Additionally, personal characteristics such as shyness and anxiety can amplify this hesitancy. The lack of personal connection and reduced nonverbal cues in online settings can further contribute to students' reluctance to participate.

Limited participation of students due to teachers' limited time. Limited student participation due to teachers' limited time is a common challenge in both online and in-person classrooms. This can arise from factors such as large class sizes, demanding curricula, or the need to accommodate diverse learning styles. As a result, students may feel less engaged, have reduced understanding of the material, and become discouraged if they feel their voices are not heard.

“...uhm... Sometimes, because uhm, in an online setting uhm teacher tends to be strict. uhm... They're focusing on how they can deliver the lesson very well in an online setting. But in face-to-face setting, they tend to have conversation, more examples. In a face-to-face setting, there are more chikas, there are more examples to understand more the lesson.” (Sometimes, in online classes, teachers can seem stricter. They're really focused on teaching the lesson effectively. But in person, they have more conversations and give more examples. There's more discussion and more examples to help us understand the lesson better.) --- P4, Lines 16-20

“...so among class sa face-to-face setting is like matagal matapos kaysa sa online setting na we're just ano delivering the lesson tapos after that, wala na, then sa face to face is like mag chika chika pa gamay, naga bonding, naga

tawtawa ganun.” (So, during face-to-face classes, it feels like it takes longer to finish compared to online classes where we just deliver the lesson and that's it. In face-to-face classes, we get to chat a bit, bond, and laugh together.) --- P4 Lines 26-29

“...Iyaha lang pong the way siya mag-teach kaya for example, na siya sa online, kay more on discussion lang siya. Like, kanang manawag siya pero murag wala may mo response. But in face-to-face, kaya um, like, magtawag siya. So, mga estudyante is maka-cooperate yung siyag taman kay pwede na niya na patindugon ba ron or kanang tagaan niya ug other tasks po.” (It depends on how the teacher teaches. In online classes, they mostly have discussions but it's hard to get students to participate. But in real classrooms, teachers can call on students and the students can easily answer or do other tasks.) P2, Lines 73-77

Teacher-student interaction is essential in all types of education, regardless of whether technology is engaged (Kuo et al., 2014). Students' interactions with educators are crucial as a strong, favorable interaction between the student and the teacher is essential for enhancing students' behavioral engagement (Nguyen et al., 2018). However, in the context of online education, research participants have highlighted several barriers to student participation. Teachers' focuses on content delivery, combined with time constraints, often limits the opportunities for meaningful interaction, reducing student engagement. Additionally, creating interactive online experiences is challenging, especially when teachers' individual styles vary, further impacting participation. These findings suggest that while teacher-student interaction is critical for engagement, the online format introduces complexities that require careful adaptation of teaching methods to foster more interactive and participatory learning environments.

Teachers' Lesson Delivery

Effective lesson delivery is essential for creating engaging and successful learning experiences. Teachers should communicate clearly, use a variety of activities, focus on student needs, use technology strategically, manage the classroom effectively, and provide regular assessment and feedback. By focusing on these key aspects, teachers can significantly improve their students' learning outcomes.

Students are scared to their teachers in online class than in in-person class. Students may feel more scared of their teachers in online classes due to anonymity, limited opportunities for building rapport, technical difficulties, and cultural differences. Teachers should be aware of these factors and strive to create a supportive and welcoming online learning environment.

“...They tend to have more difficult instructions and strict instructions like bawal in ani, bawal in ana bawal mag open ug tab. During online classes, they let us turn on our camera so our attention is fully listening to them.” (They tend to have more difficult and strict instructions like 'don't do this,' 'don't do that,' 'don't open tabs.' During online classes, they let us turn on our camera so our attention is fully listening to them.) --- P4, Lines 22-25

“...pag sa online kay murag daghan ug mga confusion about ana and dili nimo dali dali ma contact si sir kay busy pd siya and mabadlok mi.” (When it comes to online, it seems like there are many confusions about it and you can't easily contact sir because he is also busy and we are afraid.) --- P3, Line 9-11

Many students believe that online interactions are less personal and more formal, which might cause anxiety while interacting or asking questions. Students noted that actions like contributing responses or being called upon were more daunting in online settings, most likely owing to the dread of being assessed in a less familiar setting (Jaggars, 2014). Students often feel more scared of their teachers in online classes than in in-person settings due to several factors. Participants express that online classes tend to have stricter rules, such as prohibitions on opening tabs or engaging in distractions, creating a heightened sense of control and rigidity. The requirement to keep cameras on adds a layer of surveillance, making students feel more exposed and anxious about making mistakes. Furthermore, the difficulty in contacting teachers during online sessions, coupled with the perception that teachers are busy, leaves students feeling isolated and hesitant to seek clarification. This lack of immediate interaction, combined with technical challenges and confusion, amplifies students' fear and anxiety, making the online learning environment feel more intimidating than face-to-face classes.

The students can understand the lesson better in in-person than in online class. The effectiveness of in-person and online classes depends on various factors. While in-person classes may have advantages like face-to-face interaction and hands-on activities, online classes offer flexibility, self-paced learning, and access to resources. The best format for a student depends on their learning style, the subject matter, and the quality of the instruction.

“...Iyabang pagtudlo man gud sa amoa, pag sa online lang kay more on ano lang siya like discussion and wala siyay ay kanang sometimes ma-apply niya ang application pero dili kaayo niya ma-emphasize but in online man class, I mean face-to-face rather, ginapaapply man gud niya like ang mga specific task like if you are going to teamwork with your co-classmates so mag-teamwork gyud mo. But in face-to-face, ayy online kay di man gud siya mabuhat pag unsa man ninyo ug kuan na layo man mo.” (Their way of teaching us in online classes is more focused on discussions. Sometimes they try to apply what we've learned, but they don't emphasize it much. However, in face-to-face classes, they make us do specific tasks. For example, if we need to do a group project, we actually work together as a team. But in online classes, it's difficult to do that because we're far apart.) --- P2, Lines 130-135

“...Sa akoo, sir, kay personally, dili gyud kaayo ko makasabot ug online class, sir, kay ma-distract man gud ko kay cellphone man gud or di kaya laptop, o kanang mga gadgets, sir. So mas okay sa ako ang face face to face na classes kay kanang ma-put aside man nako akong cellphone kay bawal man mag cellphone kung magklase. So makafocus ko sa teacher, magsulat ug notes, para makasabot ko sa iyang klase.” (For me, sir, personally, I don't really understand online classes, sir, because I get distracted by my cellphone or my laptop, or those gadgets, sir. So I prefer face-to-face classes because I can put aside my cellphone since it's not allowed during class. So, I can focus on the teacher, write notes, and understand the lesson better.” --- P1, Lines 83-87

Good engagement between instructors and students will establish great relationships in the classroom and contribute to successful learning (Che Amad et al., 2017). Teacher-student interaction is essential in all types of education, regardless of whether technology is engaged (Kuo et al., 2014). In online classes, teaching tends to be more discussion-based and lacks the hands-on emphasis of in-person lessons. Face-to-face classes prioritize practical tasks and group work, which reinforce learning and collaboration. The physical distance in online classes makes it harder to engage in such activities. Additionally, distractions from gadgets in online settings hinder focus, whereas in-person classes provide a more controlled environment that promotes better concentration and understanding of the material.

The teachers are strict in their lessons in online than in in-person class. The perception that teachers are stricter in online classes compared to in-person classes is influenced by factors like anonymity, technical difficulties, and cultural norms. While there may be instances where this is true, it's important to consider the broader range of factors that can influence teacher behavior in both formats. The specific context of the class, the teacher's personality, and the subject matter can also play a significant role.

“...uhm.... Sometimes, because uhm, in an online setting uhm teacher tends to be strict.” ---P4, Lines 16-17

“Sa personality naman niya sir is like very strict siya. Yes sir, then like hindi siya jolly, hindi siya jolly paminawon sir.” (Well, sir, he has a very strict personality. Yes, sir, and he's not very cheerful or pleasant to listen to.) --- P3, Lines 21-22

In online classes, teachers tend to be stricter to maintain student attention and engagement. The lack of physical presence and interaction may lead to enforcing stricter rules for discipline. One participant mentioned that their teacher's strict personality made the lessons less pleasant to follow. This strictness feels more intense in online settings, where tone and formality are more prominent compared to the dynamic nature of in-person interactions.

Teachers' Overall Identity as an Educator as Perceived by the Students

Identity is seen as a fundamental component of teachers' professional development (Beijaard 2019). Teacher identity is a complex network of influences and imprints shaped by personal and professional

life experiences (Bukor, 2014). Teachers therefore face the policies and professional discourses they meet not as *tabula rasae*, but rather actively employ their prior identities to understand, learn from, assess, and adapt to the changing circumstances of their work in schools and classrooms (Buchanan, 2015). Teachers' overall identity as perceived by students is influenced by their teaching style, relationships with students, subject matter expertise, cultural background, and the school context. Understanding these perceptions can provide valuable insights into the teaching and learning process, allowing teachers to make informed decisions about their instructional practices and interactions with students.

Misconception on the identity of teachers' in online compared to in-person class. Teachers are often perceived as more friendly and approachable in in-person classes due to nonverbal cues, opportunities for informal interaction, a stronger sense of community, and cultural factors. While individual experiences can vary, teachers can also create a welcoming and supportive online learning environment with careful planning and effort.

"...Sa akoo sir kay sa akong perspective sa iya sir pag online class kaya ano lang kay diretso-diretso lang. Kaya siya parehas sa iyang kanang kung unsa siya magtudlo pag mag-face-to-face sir ba. Kay labi siya magtudlo pag face-to-face, labi pud siya magtudlo pag mag-online class. Usabay sir maglibog mi, di mi kasabot sa iyang lesson pag ing-ana gud sir ..." (For me sir, in my perspective of him sir during online class, it's like he's just straight to the point. That's why he's the same as his, like what he teaches when it's face-to-face class sir. Because he teaches differently when it's face-to-face, he also teaches differently when it's online class. Sometimes sir we get confused, we don't understand his lesson when he's like that sir...) P1, Lines 127-131

"...Para sa akoo na apektuhan siya kay confused ang student, kung strict ba siya or buotan ba siya." (For me, he is affected because the students are confused, whether he is strict or kind.) --- P4, Lines 67-68

"...The iyahang attitude towards sa amua is pasagdan na lang niya sa amua. Kami na lang magbabala sa amung learning. Kaya iya naman, gi lesson tanan." (He has a hands-off approach with us. He expects us to take responsibility for our own learning. He justifies this by saying that everything has already been taught.) ---P3, Lines 58-60

As stated by Ulla et al. Al (2024) teacher identity has gained widespread recognition as an essential element of the teaching profession that has a significant influence on teachers' attitudes, actions, and comprehension of their social duties. Students experience confusion about their teachers' identities in online compared to in-person classes due to differences in teaching style. One participant noted that their teacher is more direct in online classes, which contrasts with their approach in face-to-face settings, leading to misunderstandings. The teacher's strictness or kindness is also unclear online, making it harder for students to grasp their personality. Additionally, the teacher's hands-off approach in online classes, where students are expected to take responsibility for their own learning, further contributes to the disconnect in how students perceive them.

The students perceived the teachers as boring. Teachers can face the significant challenge of being perceived as boring by their students. This perception can be influenced by factors such as relying too heavily on lectures, delivering lessons in a monotone manner, teaching irrelevant content, lacking a sense of humor, and drawing upon negative student experiences.

"...uhm... Based on my experience here, sa online man gud is very boring sya. paminawon like, like guilty ko kayo pag mag klasi, murag daghan kaayo ug destructions like everywhere. (Uhhh... Based on my experience here, online classes are very boring. It sounds like, like I feel guilty when I'm in class, it seems like there are a lot of distractions everywhere.) --- P3, Lines 4-6

"...uhm... Sa online, sir, is medyo maboringan ko. Sa ano na, sir, kay like dili mn nako makita iyang face mn gd dili nako siya ma interact or ma observe ang interaction between us." (Uhhh... In online classes, sir, I tend to get bored. It's because, sir, I can't really see his face, I can't interact with him or observe the interaction between us.) --- P3, Lines 16-18

“...kung ma boringan ko sa lesson kay dra na nga time ma confuse ko kung unsa mn gyud gipasabot ni sir.” (“If I get bored with the lesson because it's already late, I get confused about what sir is really saying.”)
--- P3, Lines 26-27

Students typically swayed away from taking online courses due to previous negative experiences such as an unprecedented workload, lack of interaction with professors, lack of professor presence, malfunctioning electronic devices difficulties with self-teaching, and time management (Banks & Vergez, 2022). These barriers align with the responses from students, who express a lack of engagement and motivation in online classes. One respondent described online classes as "boring," attributing this to distractions, an inability to see or interact with the professor, and a lack of personal connection. The absence of face-to-face interaction, which typically fosters rapport and real-time feedback, leaves students feeling disconnected. Additionally, the timing and pacing of online lessons further contribute to confusion and disengagement, with students feeling lost or uninterested when they cannot clearly follow the professor's explanations. These responses reinforce the literature's findings, emphasizing that online learning environments, when not designed with strong interaction and support, can lead to disengagement and frustration for students.

Teachers are more friendly and approachable in in-person class. Teachers are often perceived as more friendly and approachable in in-person classes due to factors like nonverbal cues, opportunities for informal interaction, and a stronger sense of community. These factors can contribute to a more welcoming and supportive learning environment.

“...buotan diay siya sa personal or sa face-to-face na setting.” (he's actually kind in person or in a face-to-face setting.) --- P4, Lines 66-67

“...Uhmm... sa face-to-face sir, is, uhmm... mas dali nimo maano ang teacher, makasturya, then makita mo din mga personality sa teacher if face-to-face, then, ah, kani si sir, dali rin kayo siya mag-sturya, so I can ask any questions regarding among lesson. Like, di ko maulaw, di kumakulbaan sa iya kayo.” (Uhmm... in face-to-face classes, sir, it's easier to, uhmm... talk to the teacher, then you can also see the teacher's personality if it's face-to-face, then, ah, this sir, it's easy to talk to him, so I can ask any questions regarding the lesson. Like, I'm not shy, I'm not nervous with him.) --- P3, Lines 43-46

Teacher identity is a complex network of influences and imprints shaped by personal and professional life experiences (Bukor, 2014). Teachers therefore face the policies and professional discourses they meet not as tabula rasae, but rather actively employ their prior identities to understand, learn from, assess, and adapt to the changing circumstances of their work in schools and classrooms (Buchanan, 2015). This complexity of teacher identity is reflected in the responses from students, who highlight the difference in interactions during face-to-face classes compared to online settings. For instance, students noted that in a physical classroom, they are more comfortable engaging with teachers, finding it easier to communicate, ask questions, and assess the teacher's personality. This ease of interaction in face-to-face settings helps reduce feelings of shyness or nervousness, fostering a stronger teacher-student connection, which in turn enhances student participation and engagement. The students' responses underscore the significance of teachers' in-person behavior and presence in shaping their relational identities, which directly impacts the learning experience.

Conclusion, Implications and Future Directions

The shift from in-person to online classes has had significant implications on teacher-student interaction, with a notable decrease in engagement during online learning. Students express that they experience less interaction with their teachers in virtual settings, which can be attributed to challenges such as limited visual cues, intermittent internet connections, and reduced opportunities for spontaneous conversations. This reduced interaction makes it difficult for students to connect with their teachers, impacting their motivation and overall learning experience. To address this, teachers need to implement more interactive

strategies online, such as real-time discussions, breakout sessions, and multimedia resources, to simulate the engagement typically seen in face-to-face classes.

Another key issue is the change in teaching style between in-person and online settings. While teachers tend to adopt a more student-centered approach in physical classrooms, the constraints of online teaching often lead to a more teacher-centered approach. This shift can restrict students' active participation and reduce their autonomy in the learning process. The limited participation seen in online classes, combined with teachers' time constraints, suggests a need for rethinking how online classes are structured. Educators should consider incorporating more collaborative activities, such as group discussions, peer assessments, and problem-based learning tasks, to maintain a student-centered approach even in virtual environments.

The perception of teachers' identities in online versus in-person classes further highlights the challenges of virtual learning. Students perceive their teachers as more approachable and personable in face-to-face settings, whereas online, teachers are often viewed as stricter and less interactive. This disconnect can lead to misconceptions about teachers' personalities, with students feeling that their instructors are "boring" or distant in the online format. To overcome these perceptions, educators need to be more deliberate in presenting their identities online, using techniques such as personalized video messages, informal check-ins, and interactive office hours to build rapport and reduce the gap between their online and in-person personas.

Looking ahead, future directions should focus on enhancing online pedagogy through professional development and improved interaction tools. Training programs can equip teachers with the skills needed to deliver content in a more engaging and interactive manner, fostering student participation. Hybrid learning models that combine the benefits of both online and in-person education could also be explored to offer flexibility while ensuring effective interaction. Furthermore, more research is needed to explore how teachers can maintain their authentic identities in online spaces, ensuring that they remain approachable and effective in fostering student engagement, regardless of the mode of delivery.

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